

"MOSAIC", a new CSP plant concept for the highest concentration ratios at the lowest cost

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Abstract. The MOSAIC project aims to develop a commercial CSP plant concept over 1GW nominal capacity. High nominal capacity is reached in a modular way, where each MOSAIC module delivers thermal energy to connected thermal energy storage systems that supply their energy to a high capacity power block (>1GW). This modular configuration significantly reduces the specific cost of the power block (€/MW installed).

Each MOSAIC module consists of an innovative fixed spherical mirror concentrator arranged in the form of a semi-Fresnel and a moving receiver driven by a low-cost cable tracking system. This configuration reduces the amount of moving parts of the entire system, lowering the cost of the solar field and keeping high concentration ratios. This will ensure high working temperatures and therefore high cycle efficiencies and cost-effective use of thermal storage systems.

Energy from the sun is collected, concentrated and transferred to the heat transfer fluid at module level, where, due to the modular concept, the distances from the solar concentrator to the receiver are much shorter than in typical solar tower technologies. As a result, energy collection efficiency is maximized, atmospheric attenuation is minimized, and precision requirements can be lowered.

All these technical benefits can contribute to a lower capital cost of the whole system, while ensuring efficiency and reliability. This therefore has a strong impact on the final cost of electricity production.

INTRODUCTION

CSP technology has great potential, but also a great need for further cost reduction. This can only be attained by reducing costs while maintaining or increasing energy conversion rates. Achieving both at the same time is a great challenge, as the goal of achieving higher efficiencies implies reaching higher operation temperatures, which in turn requires higher concentration ratios. The problem is that, higher concentration ratios normally require higher investments due to more accurate tracking systems, more sophisticated HTFs and materials, etc. On the other hand, higher working temperatures increase storage "cost effectiveness" which is also desirable.

Therefore, the challenge is to reach the highest possible concentration ratios using simple systems that can be manufactured, installed, operated and maintained at low cost, being this the main goal of the MOSAIC concept.

In a solar plant, biggest CAPEX and OPEX costs are dedicated to the vast solar field. Therefore, biggest efforts for cost reduction shall be focused in this solar plant subsystem. Moreover, as stated by different authors [1], main drivers for cost reduction of current Central Receiver (CR) plants are the required actuators for the mirrors to follow the path of the sun with the required accuracy as well as the structures needed to support big mobile reflective surfaces with required stiffness. This shows the need of focusing on the solar field for the plant implementation cost reduction, especially on mirror actuation (drives) and mirror support structures.

Another question that should be noted is that larger power blocks and storage systems result in lower cost. In the case of current CR plants, this means huge towers and thousands of heliostats located at long distances (>1km). This,

in turn, requires higher tracking and canting accuracy, as well as more expensive structures, and implies important atmospheric attenuation, which in practice, limits the maximum size of the plant. However, concentration ratio is a dimensionless concept, so there is no need for large infrastructures to reach high concentration ratios and high working temperatures efficiently. In fact, large collection areas (needed to increase nominal power and cycle efficiency) can be more easily achieved in a modular way, thus avoiding high accuracy requirements and unwanted atmospheric attenuation faced by large solar towers.

APPROACH

The MOSAIC concept aims to reach low-cost high efficiencies using 3D solar concentration units with spherical fixed reflectors and moving receivers, grouping several of these concentration units in a high-efficiency modular plant. This can slash costs of the solar field and, in particular, those of the tracking systems and the structures supporting the reflectors. Moreover, the modular plant consisting of several identical units will share a large, efficient and cost-effective storage and power block, while keeping optical efficiency to the highest level.

It is well known that in a parabolic reflector, all incoming light rays that are parallel to the axis of the parabola concentrate in its focus. If the rays do not come from a direction parallel to the symmetry axis, the light is no longer concentrated. In a spherical reflector [2], all parallel rays coming from any given direction are reflected along a line drawn through the centre of the sphere and parallel to the direction of the incident rays (see Fig.1). This allows the reflectors to be fixed while the receiver follows the path of the sun as proposed by, for example, patent no. US4170985 [3] in 1977.

FIGURE 1. (a) Operating mode of a spherical reflector [2] and (b) patent no. US4170985 on the right [3]

Nevertheless, this concept requires huge civil works when the modules are of a certain size [4, 5]. This is especially true when they are installed in relatively high latitudes. The effect of concentration in a single focal line also appears for a series of concentric spheres of different radius (see Fig.2). Larbi [4] developed numerical models that allow to optimise the system, reducing the reflector infrastructure investment with the minimum reduction in energy delivery.

FIGURE 2. (a) Raytracing for concentric spheres [5] and (b) different approaches to the Fresnel configuration

On the other hand, one of the main problems related to the tracking systems of past fixed mirror developments is the high monetary cost of the proposed solutions. The big size and complexity of the structure supporting the receiver made this an expensive solution [6]. Practical implementations of previous developments were based in a structure with a tripod-type configuration [7, 8], as shown in Fig.3. In order to assure an accurate positioning of the receiver, the tripod and the arm holding the receiver must be stiff. This leads to heavy structures which cost grows quadratically to system size.

FIGURE 3. (a) Receiver's tracking system of previous development JOR3960046 and (b) Arecibo Observatory

On the contrary, other spherical optics systems, such as the radio telescope at the Arecibo Observatory, demonstrated that simple, low-cost solutions based on cables could be adopted to actuate its radio receiver. Transferring this idea to the MOSAIC concept is not straightforward, but a similar approach could be envisioned. The linear receiver can be suspended and actuated by a series of cables, which orient the receiver with the incoming light rays. These cables will be suspended by simple low-cost vertical stands and actuated with the required drivers.

Moreover, a modular approach is proposed. In this way, stands can be shared by adjacent modules, so that each stand will support the cables of the surrounding modules, resulting in a cost-effective implementation. All these concepts open up an enormous range of possibilities/alternatives. In particular, the proposed approach (fixed-mirror design, low cost tracking receiver system and modular configuration) could dramatically reduce the investment cost of solar plants. However, it has never been explored and even less validated in a relevant environment

TABLE 1. Previous projects that developed fixed spherical reflectors

	Experience 1	Experience 2	Experience 3	Experience 4	Experience 5	Experience 6	Experience 7	Experience 8
Description	Hemispherical reflector plant	Hemispherical reflector plant	Hemispherical Fresnel reflector	Semi-Fresnel fixed reflector				
Photograph								
Date	1970's	1970's	1990's	2000's	1980's	Late 1990's	Early 2000's	2004
Validation site	Crosbyton, TX, USA	Haifa, Israel	Auroville, India	Armenia	Marseilles, France Recife, Brazil	Republic of Crete	UK	No experimental validation
Size	19.7m diameter	10m diameter	15m diameter	Data not available	10m diameter	30m diameter 110kWt / 35kWe	Proof of concept	Theoretical design
HTF temp	Steam at 538 °C	Data not available	Steam	Air at 850°C	Data not available	Air at 850°C	-	-
Status	Decommissioned	Decommissioned	Still in operation	Not completed	Decommissioned	Decommissioned	-	Positive techno-economic analysis

After reviewing all previous attempts (see Table.1), the MOSAIC project looks more deeply into these concepts and analyses the best ways of implementing them, evaluating the advantages and disadvantages of the possible options from the theoretical and practical point of view. According to the obtained conclusions, a detailed design of the plant module has been worked out. Additionally, a scaled prototype of the module has been also designed and will be installed and operated to validate the concept.

Improvement Potential

MOSAIC modular plant configuration is based on a hemispheric semi-Fresnel fixed reflector, an actuated receiver working at high temperature. This system aims at the following benefits:

- **Low cost plant implementation, operation and maintenance** by using a fixed mirror strategy. Instead of having to purchase and install tracking systems on every reflector on the field, only actuation systems on receiver

will be needed. This minimizes the number of mobile elements on the solar field, thus reducing the CAPEX as well as the Operation and Maintenance costs compared to other CSP technologies.

- **High concentration ratio (C)** which in turn enables a high thermal efficiency of the system and the connected thermodynamic power cycle, reducing electricity costs.
- **Higher operating temperatures** compared to Parabolic Trough and equivalent to Solar Towers CR. Therefore, not only thermal efficiency is increased but also the cost effectiveness of the corresponding sensible heat thermal energy storage systems [9], due to the reduction in the required mass of thermal energy storage media.
- **High power cycle efficiencies**, since modular concepts have no size limit. Even plants as big as 1GW could be foreseen, thus the most efficient power blocks and Thermal Energy Storage (TES) could be implemented while avoiding atmospheric attenuation effect.
- **Tailored power generation capacity**, because modularity allows for an implementation tailored to specific power needs

The combination of low plant implementation and O&M costs, high solar-to-electric conversion efficiencies, and cheap thermal energy storage forms a very promising approach that is worth developing.

DEVELOPMENT; HOW TO IMPLEMENT THE CONCEPT AT REAL SCALE

A key feature of the MOSAIC concept is its flexibility, which allows the main parameters (tilt angle, surface and shape of the reflective surface, receiver length, etc.) to be modified to obtain the best performance in each situation (location, available supply chain, type of soil, etc.).

Within the MOSAIC project several analyses have been carried out in order to define the optimal configuration of the MOSAIC module. That is, the one that balances the need to reduce costs and maximize production. Prior to the optimization process, several constraints have been identified for each component. As a result, the most suitable latitudes for the technology have been identified and, for these locations, the optimum parameters of the system (geometry, number and distribution of the rings forming the module, the optimum tilt angle, the optimum working space to be covered, etc.) have been defined in terms of annual thermal energy per reflective area and cost. In addition, the size and configuration of the corresponding receiver as well as a suitable tracking system have been designed.

Design process; defining the optimum MOSAIC plant

The design of the system will depend to a large extent on the latitude of the site. It will define the tilt angle of the solar field and will have a great influence on the tracking system. In fact, a solution obtained for one range of latitudes may not be valid for another. Therefore, an analysis of Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) has been performed to determine the most appropriate range of latitudes.

The DNI level in all populated locations (therefore with a potential need for electricity supply) has been analysed and grouped by latitudes. Fig.4 summarizes the results. Consequently, the system design has been conceived for a range of latitudes between 30° and 40° N, and the results shown in this article correspond to latitude of 30.5°N.

FIGURE 4. Inland populated locations (1° latitude x 1° longitude) with a DNI value greater than 2000 kWh/m²-year

Defining the optimal solar field

Sanchez [4] showed that the minimum LCOE values for this concept will consist neither in an ‘Actual Sphere’ nor in a ‘Fresnel-Sphere’ configuration but in a ‘Semi-Fresnel’ approach. In the figures from Table 2 these configurations, ‘Actual Sphere’, ‘Fresnel Spheres’ and ‘Semi-Fresnel’, are shown as well as a calculation of the annual contribution (kWh/m^2) of each part of the reflector and the corresponding concentration ratio along the receiver.

TABLE 2. Analysis of implementation approaches for spherical concentrators.

After a cost optimization process, the optimum opto-geometrical-thermal design can be found. This optimization includes not only the optimum size and tilt angle (θ) of the system but also the selection of the number of curvatures (spheres), its configuration and the selection of the mirror area that will be finally implemented. Moreover, the optimization process takes into account practical restrictions and the impact of each selection on the cost, assuring system viability and minimizing the final cost of energy. Fig.5 shows the key geometrical parameters to be defined.

FIGURE 5. (a) Main geometrical parameters and (b) Cross section of a MOSAIC module

As it has been shown at Table 2, it should be kept in mind that not all mirrors in the field will bring the same amount of energy to the system. In the final design (see Table 4), when Mirrors providing less than $400\text{kWh/m}^2 \cdot \text{year}$ are removed, the energy supply is reduced by 3%, but the total cost of the solar field is reduced by 38%, which means a reduction in the overall cost of energy (€/kWh) of 37%.

On the other hand, the solar flux distribution along the receiver length is far from homogeneous. Solar radiation is concentrated in the line from the centre of the sphere to the mirrors but only in the lower half. Within this zone, the radiation is not homogeneous either, but it grows from the part closest to the mirrors to the point at $R/2$.

This is clearly reflected in the distribution of total energy received at each point of the receiver over a year, shown at Fig.6. In this case, the corresponding reflector consists of a central cap ($R=20\text{m}$) and three rings corresponding to spheres of increasing radii. Accordingly, there are 4 zones of maximum concentration corresponding to the 4 spheres that make up the concentrator.

The lower part of the receiver is exposed to a low level of radiation. This means that the highest efficiency (maximum energy collected and minimum thermal and pumping losses) corresponds to the receiver top part, and thus it can be shortened by removing its bottom part. In addition, shorter receivers are cheaper and easier to move. Taking all these factors into account, the optimal design corresponds to a 6m long, i.e. 4 m shorter than the theoretical one.

FIGURE 6. Accumulated flux on the receiver along the year

Additionally, it must be considered that the flux reaching the receiver surface at a given moment is further uneven and it also varies throughout the day and from one day to the next. Fig.7 shows the instantaneous flux over the receiver on the 21st of March at three different times of the day.

FIGURE 7. Instant flow over the receiver on the 21st of March at 8:00h, 10:00h and 12:00h.

In order to maximize receiver efficiency and assure thermal stability within this wide range of working conditions, different alternatives (such as external tubes receiver and helical receiver) are under techno-economical evaluation.

In addition, a system must be designed capable of placing the receiver in the required position at each moment of the day. At the early and late hours of the day, the receiver must reach higher positions to align itself with the sun and the centre of the sphere, which imposes tougher requirements on the tracking system. On the other hand, low energy is available in the morning or evening (Fig.8a shows the annual energy contribution from each solar angle). With all

this in mind, the workspace that the tracking system must reach has been defined. Fig.8b shows the tracking configuration proposed for the system.

FIGURE 8. Annual energy contribution from each solar angle (azimuth and zenith) (a) and proposed tracking configuration (b)

The MOSAIC approach banks on a modular concept, so the plant modularity has also been analysed. The modular concept could be applied either to small distributed systems or to big centralized plants. In a single module configuration, the CSP plant is made of a one optical collector and 5 towers (4 pulling cable towers and an additional supporting tower). Large CSP plants, will be composed of a number of identical units, each of these comprising a fixed solar field, an actuated receiver and a small HTF buffer but only two additional towers (1 pulling cable tower and one supporting tower) are required since pulling towers are shared among modules (see Table 3). All these units share a large common storage system and a single power block.

TABLE 3. Modular approach allows to share elements between modules

<i>Plant view</i> <i>1 module</i>	<i>Plant view</i> <i>4 modules</i>	<i>Plant view</i> <i>9 modules</i>	<i>Plant view</i> <i>N modules</i>	<i>"Unit cell"</i>
5 towers: 4 pulling towers + 1 supporting tower	13 towers: 9 pulling towers + 4 supporting towers	25 towers: 16 pulling towers + 9 supporting towers	$N + (\sqrt{N} + 1)^2$ towers: $(\sqrt{N} + 1)^2$ pulling towers + N supporting towers	2 towers: 1 pulling towers + 1 supporting tower

RESULTS, CHALLENGES AND NEXT STEPS

As explained before, the MOSAIC plant concept has been developed. The plant design has been optimized for those latitudes that are more promising (30°-40°) and a scaled prototype module will be installed in Navarra (Spain) to validate the concept. The construction phase of the prototype will begin in November 2018 and testing will begin in spring 2019 so it is expected to present the first results at SOLARPACES 2019.

These tests will allow to validate the designs and components developed within MOSAIC project. This will be mainly focused on assessing the practical feasibility and the limitations of the proposed tracking system and obtaining relevant information to estimate more accurately the manufacturing and assembly costs in the deployment phases of the technology. As a result, the most promising cases for commercial applications (distributed and large plants) will be defined.

The main characteristics of this prototype as well as those of a real plant module optimized for a latitude 30.5° are summarized in Table 4.

TABLE 4. Main characteristics of a plant module located at latitude 30.5° and the validation prototype under development

Optimized Module		<p>Latitude= 30.5°</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 rings • $R = 20m$ • Tilt angle= 7.18° • $R_{form} = 72.4m$ • $incrR = 2.16m$ • Receiver $\varnothing = 0.3m$ • Receiver length= $6m$ • $519 kW$ • $1000 m^2$ mirrors • $1176 MWh$ • Winter ($>200 kW$): $5.25h$
Validation prototype		<p>Latitude= 42.59°</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 rings • $R = 15m$ • Tilt angle= 15° • $R_{form} = 30.5m$ • $incrR = 1.3m$ • Receiver $\varnothing = 0.3m$ • Receiver length= $4.5m$ • $317 kW$ • $600 m^2$ mirrors • $710 MWh$ • Winter ($>115 kW$): $4.5h$

CONCLUSIONS

As part of the H2020 MOSAIC project, an innovative CSP plant concept is being developed. The main advantages of this concept are the following: the entire concept is fully modular, the basic configuration of each module consists of a fixed semi-Fresnel spherical mirror and a mobile receiver, which leads to a high-concentration (3D concentration) optical system that minimizes the number of moving parts.

During the project the concept is being validated and the main components are being developed: solar field, receiver and tracking system. At the end of the project it is expected to have a design that allows the highest concentration ratios and, therefore, the highest temperatures and efficiencies at a lower cost than the current existing technologies.

To achieve this goal, two fundamental challenges must be overcome. On the one hand, the cost of the fixed mirror concentrator should be kept low. On the other hand, the new low-cost cable-based tracking system should ensure the required accuracy. Finally, long-term performance and reliability of the linear receiver must be guaranteed while operating at high temperature and under highly demanding flux.

After a techno-economic analysis and the subsequent optimisation process, a first plant design was carried out with encouraging results. In addition, a "validation prototype" has been designed that will be installed during 2019 and evaluated during 2019 and 2020. With the results obtained, the concept will be improved, and a commercial plant model will be proposed.

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REFERENCES

1. K. R. Bhargava, F. Grossb, P. Schramek, Life Cycle cost optimized heliostat size for power towers Energy Procedia 49 (2014) 40 – 49 SolarPACES 2013
2. “Solar Energy Systems Design” by W.B.Stine and R.W.Harrigan (John Wiley and Sons, Inc. 1986)
3. B. Authier, Solar energy collector, US4170985A, 1977, <http://www.google.com/patents/US4170985>
4. Larbi, A.B., “A New Design of a Fresnel Collector with Fixed Mirrors and Tracking Absorber”, Journal of Solar Energy Engineering, May 2000, Vol. 122 pp 63-68.
5. Sanchez, M., et al., “Potential of Optimized Non-Tracking Mirror Concentrators for Distributed Solar Applications”, Solar PACES, 2004: Oaxaca, Mexico
6. Subramanyam, Savithri. Simulation of the Crosbyton Receiver. Thesis (Ph.D.) Texas Tech University, 1986.
7. Hariharan Shankar, Simulation of the receiver in a fixed-mirror distributed focus solar power system, PhD Thesis, Texas Tech. University, August 1981.
8. Construction and Testing of a pilot 1MW solar thermal power station using an innovative heat exchanger concept, Project reference: JOR3960046, Funded under: FP4-NNE-JOULE C, http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/37133_en.html
9. Kolb, G.J., et al., Heliostat cost reduction study, 2007, Sandia National Labs: Albuquerque, New Mexico, USA.